

THE IMPORTANCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND DIGITAL ECONOMY TECHNOLOGIES IN SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. This article examines the impact of the digital economy and artificial intelligence technologies on the development of society. The digital economy creates new forms of economic activity, allowing them to be carried out more efficiently and quickly. The article is devoted to the study of the development of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies and their presentation as a fundamental basis for the concept of the digital economy, implemented within the framework of Industry 4.0. The purpose of the study conducted in the article is to analyze the areas of effective application of AI methods and tools, as well as to assess the possibilities of implementing AI in the business sphere. The theoretical and practical aspects of the application of artificial intelligence technologies in various sectors of the economy are considered. It was found that the high cost of implementing the technology and determining the stages of its work is a serious obstacle to the use of artificial intelligence.

Keywords: digital economy, artificial intelligence, e-commerce, financial technology, industrial application, business processes, digital marketing, development, industry.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В РАЗВИТИИ ОБЩЕСТВА

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается влияние цифровой экономики и технологий искусственного интеллекта на развитие общества. Цифровая экономика создает новые формы экономической деятельности, позволяя осуществлять их более эффективно и быстро. Исследуются вопросы развития технологий искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) и их представления

как фундаментальной основы концепции цифровой экономики, реализуемой в рамках Индустрии 4.0. Целью проведенного в статье исследования является анализ областей эффективного применения методов и инструментов ИИ, а также оценка возможностей внедрения ИИ в бизнес-сферу. Рассмотрены теоретические и практические аспекты применения технологий искусственного интеллекта в различных отраслях экономики. Установлено, что высокая стоимость внедрения технологии и определения этапов ее работы является серьезным препятствием для использования искусственного интеллекта.

Ключевые слова: цифровая экономика, искусственный интеллект, электронная коммерция, финансовые технологии, промышленное применение, бизнес-процессы, цифровой маркетинг, развитие, промышленность.

SUN'IY INTELLEKT VA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT TEKNOLOGIYALARINING JAMIYAT RIVOJLANISHIDAGI AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyot va sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining jamiyat rivojida ahamiyatini yoritish, shuningdek raqamli iqtisodiyot iqtisodiy faoliyatning yangi shakllarini yaratib, ularni yanada samarali va tez amalga oshirish imkonini beradi. Maqola sun'iy intellekt (AI) texnologiyalarini rivojlantirishni o'rganish va ularni Industry 4.0 doirasida amalga oshirilgan raqamli iqtisodiyot kontseptsiyasining fundamental asosi sifatida taqdim etishga bag'ishlangan. Maqolada olib borilgan tadqiqotning maqsadi AI usullari va vositalarini samarali qo'llash sohasini tahlil qilish, shuningdek, AI ni biznes sohasiga joriy etish imkoniyatlarini baholashdir. Iqtisodiyotning turli tarmoqlarida sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarini qo'llashning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Aniqlanishicha, texnologiyani joriy etish va uning ishlash bosqichlarini belgilashning yuqori bahosi sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishga jiddiy to'siq bo'lmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli iqtisodiyot, sun'iy intellekt, elektron tijorat, moliyaviy texnologiya, biznes jarayonlari, raqamli marketing, rivojlanish, sanoat.

Introduction

Today, the digital economy and artificial intelligence technologies are fundamentally changing not only economic processes, but also the social and cultural spheres of society. These technologies serve to accelerate economic

growth by increasing efficiency, creating new opportunities and automating work processes in various areas [1]. The digital economy makes it possible to transfer all economic processes to digital platforms, effectively use information and establish fast connections with global markets. And artificial intelligence provides such opportunities as optimizing complex and comprehensive processes, increasing the accuracy of decision-making and forecasting the situation based on real-time data. The digital economy is an economic system formed on the basis of digital technologies and the Internet. Artificial intelligence (AI) plays an important role in this system, as it helps improve data analysis, decision-making and automation processes. Innovative solutions such as cloud computing, big data, artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT) and blockchain play an important role in the digital economy. These technologies allow for quick and efficient data analysis, creation of new services and products. This article discusses the stages of artificial intelligence development in the digital economy. In the digital economy, data-driven decision making is essential. Businesses and organizations improve their competitiveness by collecting, analyzing, and using data to determine their strategies. This process also helps them better understand customer needs. The digital economy makes it possible to automate processes. With the help of artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies, many operations are performed automatically, which speeds up work processes and reduces costs. Innovative solutions, such as the creation of new products and services, are one of the main drivers of the digital economy.

Figure 1.

Revenue growth rate of the global AI market from 2016 to 2025 *

* Compiled by the author.

Statistics show that between 2016 and 2019, global artificial intelligence market revenue increased by 350%, from \$3,221.8 million to \$11,283.76 million (Figure 1).

Revenues are expected to grow to \$89,847.26 million by 2025. Figure 1. Global AI Market Revenue from 2016 to 2025, USD million The impact of AI on global GDP is due to increased productivity, personalization, reduced time costs, and improved quality of products, jobs, and services. Global productivity growth is

expected to account for 55% of the total impact of AI on global GDP during the period 2017-2030 [2] .

Literature review

In 1997, the concept of digital economy was first proposed by Don Tapscott [12], an American economist. The following year, the report *Emerging Digital Economy* released by the US Department of Commerce officially opened the prelude to the development of the digital economy. The concept of digital economy is still controversial in academic circles. The more authoritative definition comes from the *G20 Digital Economy Development and Cooperation Initiative* issued by the G20 Hangzhou Summit in 2016, which proposes that the digital economy is a series of production activities that take digital knowledge and information content as important production factors, modern network information as important media, and rational use of information and communication technology as the main driving force to optimize the efficiency of economic structure. Artificial intelligence(AI), as a discipline developed based on computer science, cybernetics, and other disciplines, can simulate, extend, and expand human intelligence [13], and can continuously improve the level of survival and development. It is a technical ability to use human knowledge to discover problems, understand the world, and transform the world [14].

The rapid development of the digital economy has created a high-quality economic and technological environment for the whole AI industry [15]. In the industrial development pattern characterized by digital technology, data, a core factor of production, is required to be empowered with more details through more comprehensive and efficient technical means [16]. With the accumulation and support of massive data, the digital economy provides a broad application platform for the development of AI technology. As the production means of the AI model running, data resources run through the whole life cycle of the birth, development, adjustment, and abandonment of the AI model. The accumulation of big data in the digital economy, the innovation of theoretical algorithms, and the evolution of network facilities drive the continuous innovation of AI technology and enter a new stage of development [17]. Simultaneously, the digital economy improves the effective supply capacity among the four major sectors of the national economy (non-financial enterprise sector, financial institution sector, government department, and household sector) through the direct role, substitution effect, and penetration of digital communication technology represented by AI, which provides support for accurate decision-making. In a market environment where digital marketing backed by artificial intelligence technology allows for the full flow of all information, which can solve the problems of limited updating and mismatch of the original product information and enhance the operational efficiency of the supply chain, thus realizing the maximum benefits of the transformation and enhancement of the marketing system and ultimately improving the operational performance [18]. Moreover, it improves the core competitiveness of enterprises and obtains a relative competitive advantage in the market environment by reducing production costs, optimizing the product

structure, improving management efficiency, etc. [19]. In addition, the basic layer resources such as algorithm development platform, AIDC computing resources, and data basic services on which the development of the digital economy depends can improve the release of the value of artificial intelligence technology through multiple links, which solves the problem of scarcity of artificial intelligence productivity on the demand side in various segments of industrial development [20].

On the other hand, With the rapid development of Internet information technology, a new round of technological revolution and industrial change is in full swing. At this critical moment of historical change and convergence, artificial intelligence technologies that integrate data into systems, algorithms, and computational capabilities are evolving globally [21]. The combination of Artificial Intelligence and Big Data Economy has led to the gradual evolution of the traditional statistical economy into an intelligent digital economy, making possible economic linkages and precise data sharing which can be used for accurate economic statistics and mathematical analyses [22]. Big data would be worthless without a tool to extract more insights from it [23]. Meanwhile, AI strongly supports the digital economy. In other words, AI optimizes the rational allocation of relevant production factors and provides realistic decision-making by extracting effective information from big data, to improve the development level of the digital economy [17]. Digital communication technology represented by AI technology has realized the transformation and upgrading of traditional industries by the digital economy through the penetration effect and substitution effect [18]. If computers and the Internet are considered to provide application tools and data platforms for the development of digital technology, then AI should be regarded as an important link in transforming the indirect productivity of digital technology into direct productivity [19]. After experiencing the period of information, consumer Internet, and industrial Internet, the digital economy has entered a new stage of intelligent economy with AI as the core driving force [20].

Methodology and results

This article analyzes research, scientific articles, and practical experience. The main trends and stages of development in the field of digital economy and artificial intelligence are identified. The digital economy operates on a global scale. The Internet facilitates the exchange of trade and services between different countries and regions. This will create new markets and opportunities, and also increase competition. This article analyzes the trends and stages of development in the field of digital economy and artificial intelligence. Research and scientific articles show how the Internet has facilitated the exchange of trade and services on a global scale, and how this process has created new markets and opportunities. Increased competition was also noted as one of the important aspects. For this article, research, scientific articles and practical experience were analyzed. The main trends and stages of development in the field of digital economy and artificial intelligence were identified. This article analyzes the main trends and stages of

development in the field of digital economy and artificial intelligence [3]. Through research, scientific articles and practical experience, the processes of change and development in these areas are studied, which provides important knowledge and ideas.

The study used quantitative and qualitative methods of expert interviews. In addition, secondary data analysis was conducted. The research experts are Russian and international leaders and leading specialists in the field of artificial intelligence who have participated in the implementation of current projects in various segments (industrial production, retail, etc.). Recently, there has been an impressive leap in the development and especially the application of artificial intelligence based on the use of neural networks. Excellent results have been achieved in solving such problems as speech, image and face recognition. These technologies are based on a rough copy of the human brain and do not always give the expected results. Technologies often start working before we understand all the details of their work. Without this understanding, all sorts of events will inevitably occur. The main problem with AI theory is that the task of constructing neural networks is incorrect from the point of view of classical mathematics. Despite this, it is difficult to understand why neural networks work. Because the number of observations (training examples) is several orders of magnitude smaller than the number of specified parameters, but in practice the network still works. We don't yet have a theoretical understanding of why the network works.

Although this should not stop us from implementing these technologies. The main task of scientists is to learn how artificial intelligence technologies work as quickly as possible. In order to take AI to a new level of development and achieve predictable and reliable results, it is necessary to create a new AI theory or significantly modify the existing theory [3]. Analyzing the potential of AI, researchers began to look for new areas of its application, primarily in combination with improving business processes. The use of artificial intelligence in this area makes it possible to make business processes more flexible, abandon traditional resources and move on to the idea of integrating advanced artificial intelligence systems and people. This approach allows you to fundamentally change the interaction between machines and humans and form integrated teams of robots and people. Such teams are able to quickly process large volumes of data during production operations, learn new information and adapt to constantly changing conditions. These capabilities of artificial intelligence allow companies to redesign their business processes to significantly increase productivity and reduce costs. Thus, one of the main areas of the development and implementation of AI in the industry is business process reengineering. The other direction is that machines do what they can do (perform repetitive, monotonous tasks with large amounts of data processing) and do what people do best (dealing with ambiguous data, making judgments in complex situations, high levels of uncertainty in decision making, creativity, etc.) This direction is commonly referred to as the third wave of business transformation [4].

The development of artificial intelligence (AI) in the digital economy has

gone through several stages. In this development process, the following main stages can be distinguished:

Stages of development

1. Previous stage (1950-1970s):

- Alphabet skills and simple algorithms.
- Introduction to teaching processes and analytical thinking.

2. Classic IA (1980-1990s):

- Solving complex problems and theoretical updates.
- Expert systems and rule-based programs.

3. Product Development (2000s):

- Data-driven approaches and machine learning.
- Application of digital marketing and artificial intelligence.

4. Deep learning (2010s):

- Development of neural networks and deep learning models.
- Possibilities of automation and big data processing.

5. Economy (2020s and beyond):

- Integration of artificial intelligence into all areas of the digital economy.
- New interactive services and software for collaboration.

Early stage : The early development of artificial intelligence began in the 1950s. During this period, simple algorithms and programs were developed that could analyze data and perform simple tasks [5] .

1. **Data revolution** . In the early 2000s, the digital economy underwent major changes. As a result of the development of the Internet and mobile technologies , a large amount of data was collected. At this stage, new artificial intelligence methods such as machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) emerged .

2. **Integration stage** : In the 2010s, AI became integrated into various areas of the digital economy, such as finance, healthcare, transportation, and trade. During this period, SI systems were implemented by many enterprises and became important for optimizing their work processes.

3. **Innovation stage** : Nowadays, artificial intelligence plays a major role in creating innovative solutions in the digital economy. At this stage, artificial intelligence technologies such as natural language processing (NLP), computer vision, and robotics are widely used. Businesses use artificial intelligence to develop new products and services, improve customer relationships, and increase operational efficiency.

4. **Future stage** : The role of artificial intelligence in the digital economy is expected to become more important in the future. New trends such as autonomous systems, smart cities, and IoT (Internet of Things) will help further advance artificial intelligence. Ethical and social issues will also become important at this stage , as the implications and risks of AI will increase as it spreads.

Conclusion

In conclusion , we note that the leaders in the implementation and use of artificial intelligence in the Russian market, especially in Uzbekistan, are industrial enterprises, banks, telecommunications companies and retail enterprises. Industrial

enterprises are actively implementing automation tools for internal and production processes [3]. Recommendation services are used to monitor current processes and predict future events at all stages of the production process. Telecommunications companies use chatbots to answer customer questions, form a tariff network and use predictive analytics to calculate the likelihood of subscribers using certain services. Companies use machine learning and behavioral analytics to count fraudulent calls. AI makes it possible to predict the load on network resources and optimize their distribution according to forecasts.

The digital economy and artificial intelligence technologies cover all areas of society, opening up new opportunities for economic development and social stability. They play an important role not only in automating economic processes and increasing efficiency, but also in improving people's lives, increasing the efficiency of public administration, and accelerating the exchange of information on a global scale. Areas such as e-commerce, financial technologies, cloud storage, and cryptocurrencies allow the digital economy to create new opportunities in global economic relations and entrepreneurship.

reflect important historical and technological changes. At each stage, the role and influence of artificial intelligence increases, helping to make economic processes more efficient and innovative. In the future, the role of artificial intelligence in the digital economy is expected to increase, which will create new opportunities and challenges [5].

This article helps to understand the development of the digital economy and artificial intelligence and provides important information for researchers, practitioners and policymakers.

In general, the digital economy and artificial intelligence are one of the powerful tools for shaping the future of society and implementing a new technological revolution. Through rational and effective management of these technologies, it is possible to improve the socio-economic well-being of society.

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